

Acknowledgement

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References

1. H. S. SACHDEV, N. K. RALHAN, M. S. ATWAL, H. S. GARG and K. S. NARANG, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, **19B**, 217.
2. M. S. PAUR, H. S. SACHDEV and N. K. RALHAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, **2**, 285.
3. NG. PH. BUU-FOI, L-PETIT and N. D. XUONG, *Chem. Abs.*, 1959, **53**, 14089.
4. B. B. CORSON, R. N. SCOTT and C. E. VOSE, *Org. Synthesis*, 1941, COLL. VOL. **1**, 179.
5. RAYMOND *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, **20**, 1721.
6. SIMRAN SINGH, R. S. TANEJA and K. S. NARANG, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, **6**, 11.
7. RANDAL *et al.*, Infra red determination of organic structures, D. Van Nostrand Co. Inc., New York, 1949, p. 6.
8. J. B. CONANT and NEAL TUTTLE, *Org. Synthesis*, 1947, COLL. VOL. **1**, 345.

Studies on Heteropoly Acids of Antimony (V) Molybdates

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THE present communication deals with the formation and stability of a heteropoly acid of antimony (V) with molybdates. Previous reports¹ on such studies are inadequate.

50 ml of *M*/20 molybdic acid solution was refluxed with 80 ml of *M*/75 potassium pyroantimonate solution for 45 min. and then evaporated to crystallisation to get fine needle shaped cream coloured crystals. The observed percentage of antimony and molybdenum in the compound came to 4.28% and 41.09% respectively against the theoretical calculated values 4.31% and 41.11%. The ratio between antimony and molybdenum was 1 : 12, which agreed with the formula $H_3[(Sb Mo_{12}O_{40})] \cdot 48 H_2O$. The final representation of the formula was according to the views of Keggin².

Determination of Basicity :

By titration of the compound in the borax solution its basicity was found to be 3. To know if all the hydrogen atoms are equally ionisable under the same condition, the above titration was also done conductometrically. The result indicated that out of the three hydrogen atoms one is held differently.

Determination of Isothermals :

To find out the number of water of constitution, use was made of the apparatus described by Ray and

Sinha³ and subsequently modified by Bhattacharya and Sinha⁴. Following the usual methods of step-wise dissociation at 30° and 40°, it was observed that the number of water of constitution was 8H₂O. This agreed with the work of Scroggie and Clark⁵ with comparable compounds.

Determination of Molecular weight by X-ray : Diffraction Method :

Cryoscopic method was applied to have an approximate idea about the molecular weight which came to 2572. It is necessary to have a very accurate data for the molecular weight to know definitely whether the molecule is dimeric or single. With the help of the analysis by X-ray photography diffraction pattern of the compound the volume per unit cell *V* was found to be 3967. The crystal being orthorhombic in shape ($\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$), the number of unit cell *n* was analysed to be 4. The observed density ρ was determined by displacement method and it came to 4.64. By applying these data to the expression, $\rho = \frac{1.66 M.n}{V}$, the molecular weight of

the compound came to 2772.2 which closely agreed with the theoretically calculated molecular weight of the compound as 2781.

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References

1. O. W. GIBBS, *Proc. Amer. Acad.*, 1885, **21**, 105; *Amer. chem. J.*, 1885, **7**, 313, 392.
2. J. F. KEGGIN, *Proc. Royal Soc.*, 1934, A, **144**, 75.
3. R. C. RAY and P. C. SINHA, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1946, **44**, 790.
4. G. C. BHATTACHARYA and P. C. SINHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**, 317.
5. A. G. SCROGGIE and G. L. CLARK, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1925, **15**, 1.

A note on potential difference between two reversible electrodes, one placed in the colloidal solution and the other in the intermicellar liquid

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THE existence of a potential difference between two reversible electrodes, one placed in the colloidal solution and the other in the intermicellar liquid (separated from the colloidal solution by dialysis, ultrafiltration etc.) the two being in direct contact, has been the subject of much controversy^{1,2,3}.

Some authors^{1,2,3} think that the colloidal solution and the intermicellar liquid are in thermodynamic equilibrium and hence there should be no potential difference between the two. It may be pointed out that a system consisting of a colloidal solution in contact with the intermicellar liquid as shown in Fig. 1 is not in thermodynamic equilibrium.

Thermodynamic equilibrium will be attained only when the distribution of the colloidal particles in the parts I and II has attained a uniform value. Therefore, thermodynamic consideration does not preclude the existence of a potential difference between the reversible electrodes A and B as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The dotted line indicates the boundary between the two liquids.

Experiments have been carried out using solutions of cetyl pyridinium chloride (CPCl) (Purity 99.1%) considerably above its critical micelle concentration (c.m.c.) in vessel II as colloid and a solution of the same substance (CPCl) at the c.m.c. level^{4,5} viz., 0.0008*N* in vessel I as the intermicellar liquid. The two solutions, about 20 min after their preparations, are placed in two breakers and the top surfaces of the solutions are carefully adjusted to the same level. They are then connected by an inverted U shaped tube filled with the concentrated solution of CPCl as according to Hartley and co-workers⁵, the density of the concentrated solution is slightly less than that of the solution at the c.m.c. level. The two reversible electrodes made of Ag/AgCl are then placed in the two solutions. The reproducibility of the E.M.F. measured by the reversible electrodes is within 0.4 mv. By the time the E.M.F. measurements are started the system has already attained equilibrium as no change in E.M.F. is noticed when readings are taken at an interval of 5 minutes.

It may be pointed out that the concentrated solutions of CPCl consist of micelles^{4,5} surrounded by Cl⁻ ions forming the ion atmosphere and an intermicellar liquid in which the concentration of the molecularly dispersed CPCl is only 0.0008*N* (i.e., its c.m.c.). Therefore, a system as depicted in Fig. 1 may be taken to represent a colloidal solution in vessel II and its intermicellar liquid (equivalent to ultrafiltrate) in vessel I and the two are connected directly (without the salt bridge of saturated KCl commonly used).

The potential difference at the liquid/liquid junction should be very small, since the system satisfies the condition which is prescribed for the determination of the electrophoretic velocity of colloidal

particles by the moving boundary method⁶. In the measurement of E.M.F. by the potentiometric method no current flows through the two solutions and so, the distortion of the electrical double layer surrounding the micelles caused by the flow of current in the electrophoretic measurement will be absent in this case. Therefore, the conditions of measurement adopted by us is the most favourable for minimising the potential difference at the liquid/liquid junction. One is, therefore, justified in assuming that the E.M.F. observed is mainly due to the difference of potential between the two reversible electrodes dipped in the two solutions.

The results are recorded in the Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1

Temperature—25°

Expt. No.	Stoichiometric concentration of CPCl in gram. equiv./lit.		E.M.F. in mv
	Vessel I	Vessel II	
1	0.0008	0.008	10.0
2	0.0008	0.016	17.5
3	0.0008	0.032	30.5
4	0.0008	0.064	57.6
5	0.0008	0.128	109.7

TABLE 2

Temperature—25°

Expt. No.	Stoichiometric concentration of CPCl in gram. equiv./lit.		E.M.F. in mv
	Vessel I	Vessel II	
1	0.0009	0.016	13.6
2	0.0009	0.032	26.2
3	0.0009	0.064	46.4

It will be noticed from the data recorded in the Tables 1 and 2 that the potential difference between the two reversible electrodes increases as the concentration of the micelle in vessel II is increased. It, therefore, follows that the activity of the Cl⁻ ions, constituting the diffuse double layer, increases as the concentration of the micelles (i.e., the colloid) is increased in chamber II. If the data in experiment (1) in the Table 1 is examined, it will be noticed that an increase in the stoichiometric concentration of CPCl by ten times produces a difference of potential of 10 mv only between the two reversible electrodes. This is to be attributed to the fact that the CPCl molecules in excess of 0.008*N* have associated to form micelles each of which may contain 40 to 50 or more molecules, the long chain ions forming the positively charged core of the micelles and an equivalent amount of Cl⁻ ions forming the diffuse electrical double layer. Since the Cl⁻ ions in the diffuse double layer can not go beyond the boundary of this layer, they cannot register their activity unless the micelle to which they belong carries them to the electrode. For this reason, the activity registered by the Cl⁻ ions is low and consequently the observed potential difference between the electrodes is small.

Again owing to micelle formation, the observed activity of the Cl^- ions may not vary proportionally with the concentration of the micelles. This fact will be evident from the following consideration.

The data in Table I shown that the difference of potential between the cells in experiment (2) and (4) is 40.1 mv. If $(a)_4$ and $(a)_2$ represent the activities of the Cl^- ions in the colloidal solutions in vessel II corresponding to the experiment (4) and (2) respectively then the following relation should hold good

$$0.059 \log \frac{(a)_4}{(a)_2} = 0.0401 \text{ volt}$$

It, therefore, follows that $(a)_4/(a)_2 = 4.79$ nearly. The corresponding increase in the ratio of micelle concentration according to Murray and Hartley⁷ and also Ghosh⁸ is equal to $\frac{(0.064-0.0008)}{(0.008-0.0008)}$ or 8.8 times approximately. Thus an increase of 8.8 times in the ratio of micelle concentration produces an observed increase of 4.79 times only in the ratio of the activities of the Cl^- ions. The experimental results, therefore, lead to the conclusion that the sol concentration effect is quite considerable even when the use of a salt bridge is avoided and the potential at the liquid/liquid junction is kept very low (if not eliminated altogether).

Further work on this line is in progress.

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References

1. A. J. RABINOVICH and V. A. KARGIN, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, **31**, 50.
2. K. SOLLNER, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1953, **8**, 179.
3. J. TH. G. OVERBEEK, *Colloid Science*, Vol. I, (Ed.), H. R. Kruyt, Elsevier Publishing Company, 3rd Reprint, 1963, p. 184.
4. G. S. HARTLEY, B. COLLIE and S. C. SAMIS, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, **32**, 795.
5. A. LOTTERMOSER and E. FROTSCHER, *Koll. Beih.*, 1937, **45**, 303.
6. A. TISELIUS, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, **33**, 524; *Koll. Zeit.*, 1938, **85**, 129.
7. R. C. MURRAY and G. S. HARTLEY, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, **31**, 183.
8. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 359.

12-Molybdophosphates of Biguanides and Related Compounds

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THISTLETHWAITE *et al.*¹⁻⁵ have prepared a number of 12-molybdophosphates of group I, group IIA, group IIB metals, ammonium and different metals of first transition series. Broadbank *et al.*⁶ have reported the synthesis of 12-molybdophosphates of alkali metals, ammonium and different organic amines. Biguanides and guanylureas are considered as strong amines and form stable normal and acid salts. 12-Molybdophosphates of Biguanides and guanylureas have been prepared by direct reaction between 12-molybdophosphoric acid and the appropriate amine carbonates and the reactions were carried out over water bath until all the effervescence ceases. The salts were isolated from the concentrated mother liquor.

Analysis: Nitrogen was estimated by semimicro Duma's method. Phosphorous was estimated acimetrically and hydron content was determined from the pH measurement of a definite amount of the salt. Thermal behaviours of biguanidium-12-molybdophosphate were studied by heating weighed quantity of salts between 50°-500° temperature in a muffle furnace and each time noting the weight losses.

All the salts are water soluble compounds and the dry crystalline salts contains large number of water of crystallization. Complete loss of water of crystallization takes occurred at about 250° and above 450° the compounds were found to decompose completely. From the Table 2 the apparent basicity of the 12-molybdophoric acid seen to be above 3. This results support the works of Thistlethwaite and others. According to Ripon¹ 12-molybdophosphoric acid has three strong hydrogens and further hydrogen of the hydrated complex can ionize under certain conditions. The additional H^+ seems to stabilize biguanide salts because at pH 7, $\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ ion becomes unstable and degraded to simpler anions.

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TABLE I

Compound	% of N	% of P	% of Mo	N : P	Water of crystallisation per $\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ ion
1. Biguanidium 12-molybdophosphate	4.42	1.42	52.7	6.90 : 1	14.12
2. Guanylurea 12-Molybdophosphate	3.40	1.35	51.1	5.58 : 1	15.70
3. Ethylbiguanidium 12-Molybdophosphate	4.49	1.39	—	7.14 : 1	12.11
4. Phenylbiguanidium 12-Molybdophosphate	4.54	1.29	—	7.79 : 1	16.09
5. Guanylurea-O-Ethylether 12-Molybdophosphate	3.34	1.39	—	7.39 : 1	12.87